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A Creative Folio

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lakbaydiwapublishing@gmail.com
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CARLITO C. BIALES, PhD

Assistant Professor IV

Eulogio Amang Rodriguez Institute of Science and Technology

NCR, Philippines

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Intimate Effusion

How romantic the moonlight
Through its luminescence
Two lovely silhouettes delight.
Caressing its countenance

The interspace of my sight
Trajectory of two unfamiliar paramours
The vibes of cupid light
Delighting in the mystique of glamor

The quench of lovely sparks
Reverberate from a distant sight.
It emanates the desire of the heart.
And flows within an empty light.

What a euphoric eye view
These two enchanting, picturesque
It captivates the light hue
Two souls remain still in rest.